

Electrochemistry

Selective Electrochemical Production of Ethylene from Bicarbonate Solution

Behnam Nourmohammadi Khiarak, Gelson T. S. T. da Silva, Jackson Crane, Colin P. O'Brien, Michael R. Pepe, Christine M. Gabardo, Viktoria Golovanova, F. Pelayo García de Arquer, and Cao-Thang Dinh*

Abstract: Carbon dioxide (CO₂) electroreduction directly from a reactive carbon solution (e.g., (bi)carbonate) provides a promising approach for integrating CO₂ capture and conversion. Compared to CO₂ conversion in gas-fed systems, this system typically suffers from low Faradaic efficiency (FE), especially for multicarbon (C₂₊) products. Here, we report an engineered material structuring to selectively produce C₂₊ products directly from a N₂-saturated bicarbonate solution. Multiphysics modeling studies reveal the critical role of local current density distribution and the spatio-selective evolution of C₂₊ products, which is favored in thinner catalysts (240 μm thickness). By jointly tailoring catalyst configuration and mass transport in bicarbonate electroreduction, adjusting the thickness, porosity, and surface oxidation of copper (Cu) mesh catalysts, as well as catholyte composition, we achieved a maximum C₂H₄ FE of 39% and total C₂₊ FE over 55% at 150 mA cm⁻² with a 240 μm thick Cu mesh. The system is also stable for over 160 h at 100 mA cm⁻² with maintained C₂H₄ FE over 20%. Our electrolysis system converts bicarbonate to C₂₊ with over 90% CO₂ utilization efficiency, reducing regeneration and separation costs. Optimizing catalyst pore structure, and copper surface oxide is a key to maximizing C₂H₄ production from bicarbonate solutions.

Introduction

Electrochemical CO₂ reduction (eCO₂R) has emerged as a promising technology for converting CO₂ into valuable chemicals and fuels, offering a potential solution for reducing greenhouse gas emissions.^[1–3] C₂H₄ is an attractive product of

eCO₂R, due to its large global market of ~US \$240B, and its wide use in industrial applications, including the production of plastics, resins, and fibers.^[4–6]

In many studies focusing on eCO₂R, electrolyzers typically require high-purity CO₂ supplied at elevated pressures. This process requires additional energetic steps to generate a pure gas-phase CO₂ stream and separation. Direct electroreduction of capture solution (alkaline capture solutions) could bypass the energy-intensive step of purifying CO₂ stream from the captured medium.^[7,8] eCO₂R systems have several common components: a cathode, an anode, and a separator. The cathode is where CO₂ reduction takes place, the anode is where oxidizing reactions occur (typically oxygen evolution), and the separator isolates the two reactions, and is typically a membrane which selectively transports cations or anions. Within this common architecture, there are several different configurations. In gas phase conversion cells, a gas diffusion layer at the cathode enables the diffusion of gas-phase CO₂ to the catalyst, where a triple-phase boundary (gas-phase CO₂, liquid phase electrolyte, and solid phase catalyst) facilitates the reduction reaction.^[9,10] In a dissolved CO₂ aqueous conversion system, pre-dissolved CO₂ in catholyte is supplied to the cathode surface for the purpose of reduction reaction.^[11] Finally, in direct (bi)carbonate-based aqueous conversion systems, CO₂ is generated in situ to provide dissolved and gas-phase CO₂ to the cathode surface for subsequent conversion. The local aqueous bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) can react with proton (H⁺) ions coming from membrane, specifically referring to H⁺ ions generated from water splitting within the bipolar membrane (BPM), which then diffuse through the cation exchange layer of BPM to

[*] B. N. Khiarak, G. T. S. T. da Silva, C.-T. Dinh
 Department of Chemical Engineering, Queen's University, Kingston,
 ON K7L 3N6, Canada
 E-mail: 20bnk@queensu.ca
 caothang.dinh@queensu.ca

G. T. S. T. da Silva
 Interdisciplinary Laboratory of Electrochemistry and Ceramics,
 Department of Chemistry, Federal University of Sao Carlos, São
 Carlos, SP 13565–905, Brazil

J. Crane
 Department of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, Queen's
 University, Kingston, Ontario K7P 3N6, Canada

C. P. O'Brien, M. R. Pepe, C. M. Gabardo
 CERT Systems Inc., Toronto, Ontario M6N 2J1, Canada

V. Golovanova, F. P. García de Arquer
 ICFO – Institut de Ciències Fotòniques, The Barcelona Institute of
 Science and Technology, Barcelona 08860, Spain

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the cathode side.^[12] This is resulting in the in situ formation of CO₂ [referred to as *i*-CO₂, according to equation 1 (Equation 1)].

subsequently, *i*-CO₂ can then undergo electrochemical reduction to yield eCO₂R products.^[7]

The efficient generation of *i*-CO₂ requires sufficient H⁺, which are typically provided from an acidic anodic environment via a cation exchange membrane (CEM) or generated from water dissociation within a BPM.

In direct bicarbonate electroreduction systems using a BPM, Lees et al.,^[7] demonstrated high FE of over 60% for the production of carbon monoxide (CO) and formate at current densities exceeding 100 mA cm⁻², and an FE of 34% for methane (CH₄) at a partial current density of 120 mA cm⁻². The production of C₂₊ compounds, such as C₂H₄, as primary products in bicarbonate-based systems has received relatively little attention due to the challenges associated with their electrosynthesis. Most recently, Wang et al.,^[13] have shown the significance of the local catalyst microenvironment in enhancing bicarbonate conversion to C₂H₄, achieving 31% of FE to C₂H₄ at a low current density of 100 mA cm⁻². Yet, the bicarbonate conversion systems suffer from limited local CO₂ availability and low local catalyst surface alkalinity, both of which strongly influence the FE toward C₂₊ products in CO₂ electrolysis. Also, the recent research suggests that achieving improved FE to C₂₊ products requires a balance between mass transport and catalytic activity.^[14]

Cu shows promise in C₂H₄ production via eCO₂R. Extensive research has focused on enhancing C₂H₄ FE in CO₂-fed electrolyzers through Cu-based catalyst design and local environment modification. Optimizing pH levels, electrolyte composition, and surface properties fine-tunes the local environment to boost C₂H₄ production, reduce byproducts, and control reaction kinetics and surface morphology.^[15,16]

Oxide-derived Cu catalysts improve FE toward C₂₊ products by facilitating local environment, such as high local pH, CO₂ molecule adsorption, and reaction intermediate formation, favoring C–C coupling and CO coverage at cathode surface.^[17,18] The synergy between oxide/metallic phases in Cu-based electrocatalysts enhances CO₂ activation and *CO dimerization, improving thermodynamics and kinetics for C₂ production.^[19–21] Alkali metal cations, like K⁺ and Cs⁺, affect FE by influencing intermediates' adsorption on cathodic surfaces, leading to more positive potential values for C₂ products. Anions (Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻) in the catholyte adsorb on the surface, increasing the negative charge on Cu and promoting CO protonation for C₂ products.^[22–24] However, replicating successful gas-fed reactor conditions in bicarbonate-fed reactors poses challenges due to CO₂ availability, lower bulk pH, CO₂ and bicarbonate mass transport limitation, and catalyst morphology constraints.

Here, we pursue C₂₊ product generation from bicarbonate solution by simultaneously optimizing the local environment, CO₂ availability, and catalyst thickness and porosity, together with Cu oxidation state.

We control the local pH and concentration of carbon species [e.g., CO₃²⁻, *i*-CO_{2(g)}, CO_{2(aq)}] by varying electrolyte concentration and ionic strength. CO₂ availability on the catalyst surface can be augmented through tuning the porosity and thickness of electrodes. The catalyst oxidation state was adjusted by heat treatment under ambient condition.

We observed that thinner catalysts favor bicarbonate conversion into C₂H₄. We reasoned that efficient electrolysis of bicarbonate to C₂H₄ necessitates a thin and porous electrode to facilitate the transport of aqueous bicarbonate solutions to the catalyst/membrane interface, where *i*-CO₂ can be generated. Cu catalyst oxidation state also appears to contribute significantly to the catalytic performance.

To offer physical insights into the mechanism, we have conducted multiphysics modeling, which suggests that catalyst with a thickness of 240 μm exhibits improved performance due to highly inhomogeneous local current density within the catalyst layer. Specifically, the majority of C₂₊ evolution occurs near the catalyst edges, at the interface between the membrane and the catalyst electrode layer.

In our study, we achieved a FE for C₂H₄ production of approximately 39% at 150 mA cm⁻² using a microscale Cu mesh catalyst with a thickness of 240 μm. We demonstrated a total C₂₊ production of over 55% at 150 mA cm⁻² and a high CO₂ utilization efficiency of over 90% at all tested current density ranges. Through a regeneration strategy with alternating “on” (300 s) and “off” (200 s) electrolysis segments, we maintained high selectivity toward C₂H₄ of over 20% for over 160 h at a current density of 100 mA cm⁻².

Results and Discussion

The Electrolyzer and System Configuration

The bicarbonate electrolyzer used in this study was a membrane electrode assembly (MEA) electrochemical cell with an active area of 2 cm² (Figure 1a). A BPM operating under reverse bias was used to separate cathode and anode in the MEA cell. The bicarbonate solution was purged with N₂ for 10 minutes prior to the reaction and continuously purged during eCO₂R. During the CO₂ reduction reaction, water is dissociated into H⁺, which migrate through the cation exchange layer to the cathode, and hydroxyl ions (OH⁻), which migrate through the anion exchange layer to the anode (Figure 1a). At the nickel (Ni) foam anode, OH⁻ ions are oxidized to form oxygen (O₂) and H₂O. Meanwhile, the H⁺ ions at the cation exchange layer (CEL)/cathode interface react with HCO₃⁻ to generate *i*-CO₂ (Equation 1), which is then reduced to hydrocarbons on the surface of the cathode.

Catalyst Structure Effect

It is well documented that modulating the electrode surface microenvironment can help to enhance electrocatalytic eCO₂RR efficiency. Surface roughening—such as through oxidation—can increase the density of active sites and expose specific facets, which locally concentrates CO₂ and

Figure 1. a) Schematic representation of the bicarbonate electrolyzer used in this work to produce C_{2+} from a reactive carbon solution (KHCO_3), b)–d) Schematic representation of catalysts with different thicknesses (Cu mesh 200*200 PPI); (b) $\sim 1040 \mu\text{m}$, (c) $\sim 650 \mu\text{m}$, and (d) $\sim 240 \mu\text{m}$, and e)–g) the FE of products over the Cu mesh with different thickness.

improves reaction performance.^[25–28] Additionally, free-standing porous metals have demonstrated the feasibility of utilizing the entire cathode in catalytic systems, offering advantages in terms of structural stability and electrochemical activity. In our experimental endeavors, we initially examined the performance of an untreated Cu mesh (Figure S1a) in 1 M KHCO_3 as a potential cathode material for direct bicarbonate conversion. However, our findings revealed significantly low C_2H_4 FE of less than 2% (Figure S1a). This suboptimal performance can be attributed to poor active sites (not selective for eCO_2RR) and local environment to stabilize key intermediates like CO adsorption and CO–CO for the formation of C_{2+} products, which limit their effectiveness in absorbing and reducing CO_2 molecules. Consequently, we turned our attention to testing oxide-derived Cu materials, aiming to exploit their unique properties and potentially enhance the electrocatalytic performance of the system.

Next, we conducted tests on a Cu mesh that was pretreated with heat treatment (HT) at 340°C for 3 h in the air atmosphere. As the results show (Figure S1b), the HT Cu mesh exhibited an 8.5% FE for C_2H_4 production at 150 mA cm^{-2} in 1 M KHCO_3 catholyte, while the untreated Cu mesh showed an FE of approximately 1% for C_2H_4 at the same current density. This corresponds to 8.5 times increase in FE for C_2H_4 production following the HT of the Cu mesh at 340°C compared to the untreated Cu mesh. Although the

HT Cu mesh exhibited an 8.5% FE for C_2H_4 at 150 mA cm^{-2} , this performance is relatively low compared to reported performance for direct bicarbonate conversion (Table S1). It was hypothesized that the elevated concentration of KHCO_3 might buffer the local catalyst surface, leading to a significant decrease in C_2H_4 FE. Given that the H^+ flux originated from the BPM in proximity to the catalyst surface, we decreased the KHCO_3 concentration to lower its buffer effect and introduced KCl to leverage the shielding effect of K^+ ions and mitigate the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) interference. So, we have chosen 0.1 M KHCO_3 + 0.9 M KCl catholyte to test our hypothesis.

We investigated the effect of catalyst structure on direct bicarbonate electroreduction to C_2H_4 using heat-treated Cu-based samples. We tested three different catalyst configurations: i) five layers of stacked Cu meshes with a total thickness of $1040 \mu\text{m}$, ii) three layers of stacked Cu meshes with a total thickness of $650 \mu\text{m}$, and iii) a single layer of Cu mesh with a total thickness of $240 \mu\text{m}$. All Cu meshes used in this study had a porosity of 200 Pores Per Inch (PPI) (Figure 1b–d). The electrochemical reduction in 0.1 M KHCO_3 + 0.9 M KCl solution was tested on each of the electrode materials at various current densities, for identical HT of 340°C for 3 h under ambient condition. The five layers of stacked Cu meshes with a thickness of $1040 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 1b) produced almost entirely H_2 under all screened

current densities, with a small amount of C_2H_4 (~9%) at a current density of 200 mA cm^{-2} with a less than 5% FE for ethanol and total C_{2+} FE < 12% (Figure 1e). A cathode with three stacked layers of Cu meshes, having a total thickness of around $650\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ (Figure 1c) demonstrated improved performance, with a maximum C_2H_4 FE of ~20% at 200 mA cm^{-2} and total C_{2+} FE of ~28.5% (Figure 1f). Reducing the number of layers of Cu mesh to a single layer (Figure 1d), a maximum C_2H_4 FE of 36% at 150 mA cm^{-2} was achieved with total C_{2+} FE ~50% (Figure 1g). CH_4 is another product observed with an FE in the range of 0.5–6% at all applied current densities for all samples (Figure 1e–g). The full cell voltage for single-layer Cu mesh substrate was 3.8 V at the current density of 50 mA cm^{-2} and increased to 4.2, 4.5, and 4.95 V at the current densities of 100, 150, and 200 mA cm^{-2} , respectively (Figure S2). The time dependencies of the full cell voltage for different cathode configurations are shown in Figure S2a–c.

As demonstrated in the above observations, each of the cathode configurations with different porosity and thickness exhibited distinct activities in bicarbonate conversion (Figure 1b–g). We reason that the single-layer Cu mesh facilitates more efficient mass transport compared to the stacked Cu meshes. Additionally, as the catalyst thickness increases, the CO_2 availability at the flow plate-catalyst interface decreases due to the longer diffusion path. This depletion of $i-CO_2$ results in higher resistance and overpotential for CO_2 conversion at the outer layers, which, in turn, increases the HER activity and reduces the selectivity for C_2H_4 .

Furthermore, we reason that a thicker catalyst would promote HER at sites far from the catalyst-membrane interface. This is attributed to the reduced CO_2 availability with increasing distance from the BPM. Previous work has suggested that the majority of CO_2 conversion takes place within 50 to $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ from the catalyst-membrane interface.^[29] Therefore, our experiments with substantially thicker catalysts may extend to greater distances from BPM, where HER becomes dominant. Next, we have employed multiphysics modeling to explore local pH and CO_2 availability on the catalyst surface to further support our hypothesis regarding lower C_{2+} product FE for thicker cathodes.

It should be noted that the CO_2 conversion efficiency of the HT Cu catalysts improve over time. As shown in Figure S2d, initially the catalyst demonstrates ~30% FE after 10 min of the reaction. Over time, the C_2H_4 FE reaches a maximum (35.5%), before declining to 28% within 3000 s of the reaction.

Modeling Reaction Environment and CO_2 Availability

To investigate our hypothesis regarding the relative catalyst thickness dependency on C_2 productivity, we performed COMSOL Multiphysics modeling of chemical species generation, consumption, and mass diffusion in different configurations to identify an optimum cathode configuration. The modeling considered the thickness of the cathode and membrane, electrocatalytic and bicarbonate buffer reactions,

electro migrative and diffusive transport phenomena, and CO_2 phase transfer (Figure 2a).^[30,31]

We hypothesized that a major contributor to the difference in performance of Cu mesh in different stacks are their thicknesses (240 to $1040\text{ }\mu\text{m}$). Several simulations were performed with varying catalyst layer thickness. As the catalyst layer became thinner, the predicted C_2 FE increased, consistent across all current densities (Figure 2b), and aligning with experimental trends. As the modeling suggests and previous studies have shown, the $i-CO_2$ concentration is high near the catalyst-membrane interface and also at the flow plate-catalyst interface (Figure S3). The low CO_2 concentration in the center of the catalyst domain leads to low partial C_2 current density in that region (Figure 2c). Meanwhile, the HER rates remain relatively uniform throughout the domain. Therefore, as the catalyst domain becomes thicker, the relative contribution of HER becomes more pronounced, leading to lower overall C_2 FE for the thicker catalysts.

Effect of Thermal Treatment

To enhance the FE for bicarbonate conversion and concurrently mitigate HER, we aimed to restructure the surface characteristics of the copper catalyst optimizing heat treatment parameters such as temperature and time.

To this end, we varied the HT temperature between 180 and $480\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ each for three hours. Cu samples were subsequently reduced via cyclic voltammetry (CV) within a potential range of -0.5 to -2 V (versus Ag/AgCl), employing a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} over 10 cycles in a three-electrode H-cell system. A representative CV curve is shown in Figure S4 for Cu treated at $340\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h under ambient condition. As can be seen the current response decreases with increasing cyclic number (the first three cycles are shown in blue and the final three cycles in red), which is attributed to the reduction of Cu oxides, and activation of the surface. This was performed after HT at each temperature. Figure 3a–d provides clear evidence of surface morphology variations under different HT conditions. At $180\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, minimal agglomeration is observed (Figures 3a and S5c,d) compared to the untreated Cu mesh surface (Figure S5(a,b)) and the unreduced Cu mesh after HT (Figure S5(e,f)). However, as the temperature increases, the formation of a nano-needle morphology becomes evident (Figure 3b–d). Notably, at $480\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the surface is covered with sparser and thicker nano-needles (Figures 3d and S6(a–c)). Electrochemical bicarbonate conversion tests showed that the sample treated at $180\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h exhibited a maximum ~12% FE for CH_4 and ~19% FE for C_2H_4 at current density of 150 mA cm^{-2} (Figure 3e), likely due to partial oxidation of the Cu surface. Under the HT condition of $250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a maximum C_2H_4 FE of 24% was achieved at 150 mA cm^{-2} current density (Figure 3f). SEM images of the sample treated at $340\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ revealed a needle-like Cu morphology with a high density of surface needles (Figures 3c and S6(d–f)). This sample achieved a maximum FE toward C_2H_4 of 36% at 150 mA cm^{-2} (Figure 3g). When the temperature was further increased to $480\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the Cu mesh was fully covered with thicker and sparser needles (Figures 3d and S6(a–c)). Higher

Figure 2. a) Overview of modelled geometry, boundary conditions, and key reactions within system, b) modelled C_2 FE as a function of current density for catalysts of varying width, c) local current density within catalyst domain for HER (dashed lines) and C_2 evolution (solid lines) for the same catalyst widths as in (b) for a half-cell potential of -1.7 V (~ 100 $mA\ cm^{-2}$ total current density for all widths).

Figure 3. SEM images of electrochemically reduced Cu mesh catalysts, preliminarily heated at; a) 180 °C, b) 250 °C, c) 340 °C, d) 480 °C, and their corresponding electrochemical performance of bicarbonate reduction to C_2H_4 at various current densities e)–h). All heat treatments were performed under atmosphere conditions for 3 h.

HT temperature resulted in a drop of C_2H_4 FE to $\sim 25\%$ at $150\ mA\ cm^{-2}$, suggesting that the catalyst had surpassed its optimal HT condition.

Further characterization using X-ray diffraction (XRD) demonstrated a mix of Cu_2O and CuO phases in the crystalline structure of the Cu sample after HT at both 340 °C and 480 °C (Figure S7a). In contrast, the untreated Cu mesh exhibited only metallic Cu (Figure S7b), Cu treated at 250 °C showed the formation of only the CuO phase (Figure S7b). Although these oxides are reduced to metallic Cu during electrochemical reduction, oxide-derived Cu catalysts are known to promote alternative reaction pathways and facilitate the involvement of key intermediates in eCO_2RR . It has been shown that the local pH can increase due to the surface roughening following the reduction of Cu oxides as well as due to the specific orientation of the

reduced Cu grain boundaries. All these effects contribute to enhanced FE toward C_2H_4 .^[32,33] Moreover, oxide-derived Cu catalysts have shown to specifically absorb and stabilize the CO_2^- radicals and leading to the formation of reaction intermediates such as $*COOH$ and $*CO$. These intermediates can subsequently undergo C–C coupling to produce C_2H_4 and other C_{2+} products.^[34]

Significantly, SEM images of Cu samples before surface reduction via CV at different temperatures revealed some changes in the surface morphology of the Cu samples, likely due to surface reconstruction, a well-documented occurrence in Cu materials (Figure S8(a–h)).

Further analysis of the CH_4/C_2H_4 ratio demonstrated that higher HT temperatures yield the lowest ratio (Figure S9). As we varied the HT temperatures, we achieved a maximum C_2H_4 FE of 34% at $150\ mA\ cm^{-2}$ with a CH_4/C_2H_4 ratio of

Figure 4. Effect of heat treatment time at 340 °C on the gas FE at different current densities, a) FE of the C₂H₄ production and b) the FE of H₂ production (Cu mesh with 200*200 PPI size was used for this experiments).

0.038. Achieving high C₂H₄ FE requires both a sufficiently alkaline local pH and adequate CO₂ availability.^[35,36]

Varying the HT temperature revealed that 340 °C represents an optimal condition for C₂H₄ production. To further optimize HT, three different HT times were considered including 3, 6, and 10 h. As can be seen from results in Figure 4, at 6 h we obtained a maximum FE of ~39% for C₂H₄ at 150 mA cm⁻² with lower H₂ FE of ~35%, whereas the other conditions resulted in lower C₂H₄ FE and higher H₂ FE (Figure 4a,b). This difference could be due to the variations in oxide layer thickness on the Cu mesh surface, which varies among different HT times. However, the FE for methane remained below 2% for all conditions and current densities (Figure S10).

Effect of Catholyte Composition

The presence of various cations and anions has a significant effect on CO₂ conversion.^[37] In eCO₂RR, both protons and alkali cations electromigrate to the catalyst surface and significantly modify the microenvironment of the catalyst surface (schematic representation in Figure S11a). Using large cations like K⁺ can hinder H⁺ diffusion toward the electrode surface. Due to the shielding effect of K⁺ in solution, H⁺ diffusion to the catalyst surface is limited. However, CO₂ can easily diffuse to the electrode surface due to charge neutrality (Figure S11a). As a result, the presence of K⁺ will help to create large CO₂ surface coverage and subsequently promote CO₂ reduction. Also, anions (such as Cl⁻) can regulate the FE by affecting adsorbed *CO intermediates on the catalyst surface. To further study this effect, we tested different concentrations of KHCO₃ (Figure S11b) and the effect of K⁺ and Cl⁻ presence in the solution to show their effects. We observed that 0.1 M KHCO₃ mixed with 0.9 M KCl has the highest FE and activity toward bicarbonate conversion into C₂H₄ (max C₂H₄ FE of 36%) (Figure S11(b,c)). Although this catholyte achieved high C₂H₄ FE, further investigation revealed that the performance was not solely dependent on KCl, as similar results were obtained without it (Figure S11b). Additionally, the lower KHCO₃ concentration improves CO₂

dissolution, enhancing CO₂ availability at the catalyst surface and contributing to the greater selectivity toward C₂₊ products. Although higher KHCO₃ concentrations (e.g., 0.5 M) resulted in lower C₂H₄ FE, the optimized Cu mesh catalyst and favourable mass transport conditions played crucial roles in achieving the observed performance.^[34] Additionally, a catholyte with lower HCO₃⁻ concentration reduces buffering capacity, resulting in a higher local pH on the catalyst surface during electrochemical reduction; accordingly, higher C₂H₄ FE was observed with lower KHCO₃ concentration (Figure S11a). To further investigate the effect of electrolyte composition on C₂H₄ production, we tested KBr and KI as supporting electrolytes in our system. Our experimental results indicated that the inclusion of KBr and KI instead of KCl did not result in a significant difference in C₂H₄ FE compared to our standard electrolyte composition (0.1 M KHCO₃ + 0.9 M KCl) (Figure S11d). This suggests that, within our experimental conditions, the presence of these halide anions does not affect the production of C₂H₄ significantly.

Effect of Cu Mesh Pore Size

After optimizing the catholyte composition and HT conditions, we investigated the effect of Cu mesh pore size on the direct electroreduction of bicarbonate to C₂H₄. We tested Cu meshes with various pore sizes, including 60*60, 80*80, 100*100, and 200*200 wires per linear inch. As the meshes become finer, the C₂H₄ FE performance generally improves. The 60*60 mesh showed a maximum C₂H₄ FE of ~15% at 150 mA cm⁻², while the 200*200 mesh had a C₂H₄ FE of ~33% at 150 mA cm⁻² and the lowest H₂ FE of 42% (Figure 4a,b). The FE for CH₄ is also shown in Figure S12, and as can be seen, the methane FE for all samples is less than 5% at all current densities. We have identified two potential effects associated with changing mesh sizes. First, finer meshes are thinner, resulting in shorter effective catalyst domains. Modelling predicts that only very thin zones (approx. 1 μm) exhibit active CO₂ reduction, while HER dominates in the rest of the domain. Thus, shortening the domain would presumably improve C₂ FE.

Figure 5. Effect of Cu mesh pore size on FE for C₂H₄ at different current densities, a) FE of the C₂H₄ production and b) the FE of H₂ production, and c) long-term stability test within simulated carbon capture condition from 10% CO₂ containing gas stream (10% CO₂ + 90% N₂) under 5 min “On” and 2.5 min “Off” segments. Note that all samples are HT at 340 °C for 3 h.

After optimizing the parameters for direct bicarbonate electroreduction to C₂ products on HT Cu mesh, we conducted further evaluations on the liquid products produced using Cu mesh treated at 340 °C for 6 h at different current densities (the optimized condition). The analysis performed using 1H NMR spectroscopy revealed significant findings. A representative NMR profile is shown in Figure S13a. At a current density of 150 mA cm⁻², we achieved a maximum ethanol FE of 13.5% (Figure S13b). Additionally, our investigation showed a maximum formate FE of approximately 5.6% at 100 mA cm⁻² and propanol FE of 3.31% at the same current density (Figure S13). Combining the C₂₊ products from the liquid phase, our results indicate an overall C₂₊ liquid production of nearly 17%. Notably, C₂H₄ production accounted for approximately 39% of the total C₂₊, resulting in an impressive C₂₊ products FE of over 55% under optimal conditions. The SEM images of the Cu mesh sample treated at 340 for 6 h before and after reduction are shown in Figure S13(c-f), which are consistent with other observations for different HT conditions.

Conversion Efficiency

We measured the total *i*-CO₂ generated from the reaction between H⁺ and HCO₃⁻ (Equation 1) for the heated Cu mesh to determine the correlation between *i*-CO₂ generation

and its utilization efficiency (Figure S14(a,b)). The *i*-CO₂ was quantified by measuring the combined concentrations of C₂H₄, CH₄, and unreacted CO₂ leaving the electrolyzer, determined by GC measurement. We obtained an *i*-CO₂ generation concentration of nearly 3 mM (Figure S14a). The conversion efficiency was calculated using Equation 5 of the Supporting Information. Figure S14b shows a conversion efficiency of over 90% at all current densities, from 50 to 200 mA cm⁻², with somewhat reduced efficiencies at higher current densities. Achieving high CO₂ utilization efficiency and ensuring that the gas product stream is free of CO₂ brings substantial economic advantages as it minimizes the need for costly separation processes following eCO₂R.^[38,39]

To evaluate the stability of the catalyst, we conducted bicarbonate conversion at a constant current density of 150 mA cm⁻² and tracked the gas products over operation time. The system demonstrated a high FE for C₂H₄ between 35 to 40% for around 4 hours (Figure S15a). However, hydrogen FE increased over time (from 36% to 58%, Figure S15b), and the FE for CH₄ slightly increased from 0.5% to 3.36% over the operation time (Figure S15b). Inspired by CO₂ capture from flue gas and previous studies on the effect of pulse electrolysis on Cu catalyst stability,^[40,41] we conducted a stability test under simulated carbon capture conditions. In this experiment, we purged the bicarbonate capture solution with a gas stream mixture of 10% CO₂ and 90% N₂ and applied pulse electrolysis. The electrolysis

consisted of 300s “On” segments at a current density of 100 mA cm⁻², followed by 200s “Off” segments. Under these conditions, our catalyst operated for over 160 h with an C₂H₄ FE of 20–25% (Figure 5c). After almost 160 h the CH₄ and H₂ FE began to increase (Figures 5c and S15c). We attribute this long-term stability to the chemical and homogeneous oxidation of Cu atoms on the catalyst’s outermost surface during the “Off” periods, and CO₂ diffusion to the catalyst surface during the “Off” segments, which suppresses HER. We characterized the Cu mesh surface using SEM and XRD after 195 h of operation (Figure S16). The SEM images show surface reconstruction of the Cu (Figure S16 a–c), and XRD analysis revealed mostly metallic peaks with an intensified CuO peak (Figure S16d).

Conclusion

In this work, we show that tuning Cu mesh porosity and thickness enables the selective electrosynthesis C₂H₄ from a reactive bicarbonate solution with less than 10% volume detected CO₂ gas in the outlet gas stream (all experiments were conducted under N₂ purging). This demonstration was achieved through the systematic optimization of catalyst surface oxidation, porosity, thickness, and catholyte composition. Our results show that a cathode with a large pore size in the micron scale increases the rate of HCO₃⁻ transport, enabling higher *i*-CO₂ utilization and resulting in a high C₂H₄ FE of 39% and total C₂₊ product FE of over 55% at 150 mA cm⁻². More importantly under simulated CO₂ capture from flue gas (10% CO₂ + 90% N₂) and on/off electrolysis, the catalyst was stable for more than 160 h at a current density of 100 mA cm⁻². The bicarbonate electrolyzer system generates a gas stream with high (>90%) CO₂ utilization that is undiluted by CO₂, thereby potentially reducing downstream regeneration/separation costs, as supported by existing literature.^[12]

Supporting Information

Characterization and methods, electrochemical data, XRD patterns, and SEM images. Supporting Information is available free of charge.

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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Conflict of Interests

CERT is a company commercializing electrochemical CO₂ utilization technology.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: Cu oxide derive catalysts • Direct bicarbonate electroreduction • Electrochemistry • Ethylene production • Porosity and thickness effect

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